

Trait-Based Characterization of Leaf-Yielding Tannia: ‘Navsari Pari’

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KEY POINTS:

- ‘Navsari Pari’ is the first tannia variety in India developed for green leaf production.
- It represents the second improved tannia variety released in India after ‘Konkan Haritparni’ for corm production.
- Tannia leaves are popularly used for preparation of the

traditional dish “*Paatra*.”

- ‘Navsari Pari’ is a dual-purpose variety suitable for both leaf and corm production.
- The variety shows superior leaf yield potential compared with existing checks.

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ABSTRACT

Tannia [*Xanthosoma sagittifolium* (L.)], an underutilized aroid tuber crop, is widely cultivated in Gujarat for its tender green leaves used in traditional culinary preparations. The present study was conducted during 2019–2022 at three locations of Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari, Gujarat, to evaluate tannia genotypes for green leaf yield and quality attributes and to identify a high leaf-yielding genotype with relatively lower incidence of pests and diseases. Among the evaluated genotypes, Gujarat Tannia-1 (‘Navsari Pari’, NT-1) was identified as a promising genotype exhibiting medium plant height, erect plant habit, soft leaf texture, higher number of tillers and leaves per plant, and suitability for intercropping with high consumer preference. The genotype recorded an average green leaf yield of 7.96 t ha⁻¹, while after 270 days of planting it produced a corm and cormel yield of 10.02 t ha⁻¹ under South Gujarat conditions. Molecular characterization through DNA fingerprinting confirmed the genetic distinctness of ‘Navsari Pari’ (NT-1) from the existing variety ‘Konkan Haritparni’, thereby establishing its uniqueness. Owing to its superior leaf yield and dual-purpose utility, ‘Navsari Pari’ was recommended for release in the 55th Gujarat State Seed Sub-Committee Meeting held in August 2023 and subsequently notified in the Gazette of India (S.O. 4000(E)) in 1st September, 2025.

Key words: Green leaves, Konkan Haritparni, Navsari Pari, Tannia.

INTRODUCTION

Tropical root and tuber crops are well known since ancient times for saving mankind during food crisis. They play an important role in the

dietary habits of people living in the tropics and sub-tropics. Tuber crops produce large quality of dietary energy and have stable yield under different environmental conditions. These crops

are the third most important food crops after cereals and pulses (Green, 2003). They are the “Food Security Crops” of low income population living in remote villages and coastal plains of India. Most of the tuber crops are rich in minerals, vitamins, anti-oxidants, omega-3 fatty acids, dietary fibre, resistant starch and have many medicinal properties. Tannia are the most extensive tuber crops cultivated almost everywhere in India (Sreena *et al.*, 2023). Tannia [*Xanthosoma sagittifolium* (L.)] is an important tuber crop of aroid group ranking next to taro. In India, it is grown extensively in West Bengal, Bihar, U.P., Kerala, Gujarat *etc.* In Gujarat, tannia crop grown in South and Middle Gujarat. In South Gujarat, it is mainly grown as inter crop as well as in fruit orchards. It is mostly planted in *kharif* as well as rabi season. The leaves of Tannia mainly used for making value added products *viz.*, “*Paatra*”, *Sabji* “*Turiya-patra*” and corms of tannia are used for making *sabji* and curry. Due to non-availability of tannia varieties, the farmers are still using land races which are low yielders, late maturing and susceptible to diseases. Morphological characterization and agronomical evaluation of Tannia involve assessing its physical characteristics, such as plant height, leaf shape and corm size, as well as its growth habits, yield and response to different environmental conditions. This helps identify desirable traits and inform breeding decisions. It enables selection of superior genotypes (Mbouobda *et al.*, 2007).

The introduction of new varieties in Tannia through variety release programs is crucial for improving horticultural productivity and livelihoods in regions where this crop is grown. Variety release involves a rigorous process of evaluation, selection and testing of different genotypes to identify those with desirable traits such as high yield, disease resistance, improved quality and adaptability to diverse environments. Through variety release programs, researchers and farmers can work together to develop and promote crops that meet the needs of local communities, ultimately

enhancing agricultural productivity and livelihoods.

Clonal selection in Tannia is a method used to improve asexually propagated crops by identifying and multiplying superior clones. This process involves selecting desirable plants from a mixed population based on traits like yield, maturity and disease resistance and then evaluating their performance over several years. Through clonal selection, researchers can develop new varieties of Tannia that are high-yielding, disease-resistant and better suited to specific environments. The benefits of clonal selection include preserving desirable traits, maintaining stable varieties and effectively isolating the best genotype from a mixed population. However, clonal selection also has limitations, such as relying on existing genetic variation and being prone to new diseases and pests. Despite these limitations, clonal selection is a valuable tool for improving Tannia and other asexually propagated crops, ultimately enhancing agricultural productivity and livelihoods.

In Tannia, disease and pest management are crucial for maintaining crop quality and yield. Some common diseases affecting Tannia include root rot, leaf blight and dasheen mosaic virus, while pests like aphids, whiteflies, and nematodes can also cause damage. To assess the quality of Tannia, several parameters are considered, including corm and cormel size, shape and color, as well as cooking quality, texture and flavor (Agueguia *et al.*, 1992). Additionally, the presence of pests or diseases can impact the quality and marketability of the crop. For the Navsari Pari variety, its resistance to major pests and diseases is a key quality parameter, making it a desirable choice for farmers. By evaluating these parameters, farmers and breeders can select and develop varieties that are not only high-yielding but also resistant to diseases and pests, ultimately improving the overall quality and sustainability of Tannia production (Boakye *et al.*, 2017).

DNA fingerprinting is a technique used to identify and analyze the unique genetic patterns found in an individual's DNA. In plant breeding,

it helps establish the uniqueness of a new variety or clone, verify identity and detect genetic variation. By analyzing specific regions of the genome, DNA fingerprinting creates a unique genetic profile that distinguishes between different individuals or varieties. This technique has several applications, including variety protection, seed purity testing and genetic diversity analysis. DNA fingerprinting provides accurate identification, improves breeding efficiency and enhances intellectual property protection. In the case of the Navsari Pari variety, DNA fingerprinting can be used to establish its uniqueness and distinctness from other varieties, such as Konkan Haritparni, and verify its identity and purity, ultimately protecting the variety and ensuring its authenticity.

The newly developed variety NT-1, recommended for release as "Navsari Pari," boasts an impressive array of desirable traits, making it an attractive option for farmers in the south Gujarat heavy rainfall zone. Navsari Pari offers a significant increase in leaf yield, making it an excellent choice for farmers looking to maximize their returns. The variety exhibits high potential for corm and cormel production, providing farmers with a valuable source of income. Navsari Pari's high starch content makes it an excellent choice for various culinary and industrial applications. The variety's low fiber content enhances its cooking quality, making it a preferred choice for consumers. Navsari Pari's good cooking quality ensures that it retains its texture and flavor, making it a delight to consume. The variety's resistance to major pests and diseases reduces the need for pesticides and other chemicals, making it a more sustainable and environmentally friendly option.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Material

The study was conducted under the All India Coordinated Research Project on Tuber Crops (AICRP-TC) at the Department of Vegetable Science, ASPEE College of Horticulture, Navsari Agricultural University (NAU),

Navsari, Gujarat, India. The tannia genotype 'Navsari Pari' (NT-1) was evaluated during 2019–2022 under multi-location trials (MLT) at three centres of NAU, namely Navsari, Waghai and Paria.

Study Area and Climatic Conditions

The field experiment was conducted at the research farm of Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari, Gujarat, India. The region falls under the humid tropical climatic zone of South Gujarat characterized by high rainfall and warm temperature conditions suitable for the cultivation of tannia. The area receives an average annual rainfall of about 1500–2000 mm, mainly during the monsoon season. The soil of the experimental site is generally medium to heavy textured with good water holding capacity, which is favourable for tuber crop cultivation.

Experimental design and crop management

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design (RBD) with three replications. The crop was planted at a spacing of 90 × 90 cm following the recommended agronomic practices for tannia cultivation under South Gujarat conditions.

Morphological Characterization

Morphological characterization of tannia genotypes was carried out using IBPGR descriptor guidelines for tannia crops. Observations were recorded on important plant morphological traits including growth habit, plant height, plant spread, number of tillers per plant, leaf orientation, lamina shape, leaf margin, petiole length and petiole colour. In addition, corm characteristics such as corm shape, exterior colour and surface characteristics were also documented. The observations were assessed based on descriptor scoring as per IBPGR guidelines using visually selected representative plants in each replication.

Biochemical Analysis

The tannia genotypes were clonally selected and evaluated for yield and quality parameters.

Biochemical analysis of leaf and corm samples was carried out at the Central Instrument Laboratory, Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, N. M. College of Agriculture, Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari using standard analytical procedures.

Biochemical parameters of tannia leaves were estimated using standard analytical procedures. Starch content was determined through acid hydrolysis followed by spectrophotometric estimation. Dry matter content was determined by oven drying the leaf samples at constant temperature until a constant weight was obtained. Protein content was estimated using the Kjeldahl method, while crude fibre was determined by acid-alkali digestion method. Calcium oxalate content was estimated using titrimetric method and chlorophyll content was determined spectrophotometrically after solvent extraction.

Molecular Characterization

Molecular characterization was carried out using ISSR (Inter Simple Sequence Repeat) markers. Genomic DNA was extracted from young fresh leaves using the CTAB method. The quality and quantity of extracted DNA were verified through agarose gel electrophoresis and spectrophotometric analysis.

PCR amplification was performed using selected ISSR primers in a thermal cycler. The amplified DNA fragments were separated on agarose gel electrophoresis and visualized under UV light after staining. Clear and reproducible bands were scored for their presence or absence to assess genetic variability and molecular distinctness among the genotypes.

Statistical Analysis

The recorded yield and biochemical data were subjected to statistical analysis using standard procedures. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to determine the significance of variation among genotypes. Molecular marker data were scored in binary format based on the presence (1) or absence (0) of amplified bands and used for evaluating genetic diversity among

the genotypes. Appropriate statistical tools were used to interpret the experimental data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphological Performance

The genotype NT-1 (Navsari Pari) exhibited erect growth habit with plant span and plant height score of 3. Higher number of tillers (40) was recorded which indicates vigorous vegetative growth and better canopy development. The leaves were upright in position with lamina orientation score of 2 and entire leaf margin. Leaf shape was sagittate with lamina length to breadth ratio of 1.25 and glossy leaf surface. Petiole attachment was peltate with petiole length of 50 cm. In addition to corm characters, observations on cormel shape, exterior colour and surface morphology were recorded.

Such morphological traits enhance light interception and photosynthetic efficiency, leading to improved biomass production and crop productivity. Similar observations regarding the influence of canopy structure on yield potential in aroid crops have been reported in previous studies on tannia and other tuber crops.

1. Plant Characters

Character	NT-1 Value
Growth habit	1
Plant span	3
Plant height	3
No. of tillers	40

2. Leaf Characters

Character	NT-1 Value
Position of leaf	3
Lamina orientation	2
Leaf margin	1
Leaf margin colour	3
Leaf shape	2
Length/Breadth ratio	1.25
Leaf surface glossy	++
Upper leaf surface colour	2
Lower leaf surface colour	1
Petiole attachment	3
Petiole length	50 cm

Petiole colour (top third)	1
Petiole colour (middle third)	3
Petiole colour (basal third)	3
Petiole basal ring colour	3

3. Corm Characters

<i>Character</i>	<i>NT-1 Value</i>
<i>Corm / cormel shape</i>	1
<i>Exterior colour</i>	1
<i>Exterior surface</i>	2

Navsari Pari (NT-1) was evaluated along with its check Konkani Haritparni at three different locations viz., Navsari, Waghai and Paria centre under multi-location trial (MLT). Navsari Pari (NT-1) has recorded an average green leaves yield (7.96 t/ha) and corm & cormel yield (10.02 t/ha) which was 31.1 % and 14.8 % higher over the national check variety Konkani Haritparni, respectively (Table 1 and 2). Similar findings reported by Solomon *et al.* (2014), Godson *et al.* (2019) and Sreena *et al.* (2023).

Yield performance

Table 1: Comparative performance of Tannia NT-1 (G. Tannia-1) for green leaves yield without petiole (t/ha) at different locations in different years

Expt. and Year	Location	Yield of leaves without petiole (t/ha)		S.Em.±	C.D. at 5%	C.V.%
		Navsari Pari (NT-1)	Konkan Haritparni (NC)			
Kh-2019 PET	Navsari	8.07*	5.74	0.26	0.76	9.70
	% Inc. over		40.59	-	-	-
Kh-2020 SSVT	Navsari	8.15*	5.61	0.34	1.00	12.53
	Waghai	8.60*	6.84	0.34	0.98	10.08
	Mean	8.38 (2)	6.23(2)	-	-	-
	% Inc. over		34.51	-	-	-
Kh-2021 LSVT	Navsari	7.78*	5.81	0.27	0.79	9.99
	Waghai	7.95*	6.06	0.31	0.89	11.25
	Paria	7.93*	5.83	0.25	0.72	8.92
	Mean	7.89(3)	5.90 (3)	-	-	-
	% Inc. over		33.73	-	-	-
Kh-2022 LSVT	Navsari	7.25*	5.97	0.28	0.82	10.47
	Waghai	8.67*	6.97	0.36	1.04	10.40
	Paria	7.27*	5.77	0.31	0.91	11.51
	Mean	7.73(3)	6.24 (3)	-	-	-
	% Inc. over		23.88	-	-	-
Over all mean (9)		7.96	6.07	-	-	-
Over all % inc. over			31.1	-	-	-
Frequency of top non-significant group			9/9			

*Significantly superior @ 5 % than check

Table 2: Comparative performance of Tannia NT-1 (G. Tannia-1) for corm and cormel yield t/ha at different locations in different years

Expt. and Year	Location	Corm and cormel yield (t/ha)		S.Em.±	C.D. at 5%	C.V.%
		Navsari Pari (NT-1)	Konkan Haritparni (NC)			
Kh-2019 PET	Navsari	8.39	7.02	0.51	1.51	10.53
	% Inc. over		19.52	-	-	-
Kh-2020 SSVT	Navsari	9.37*	7.31	0.70	2.07	13.95
	Waghai	7.69	7.57	0.78	2.29	14.16
	Mean	8.53(2)	7.44 (2)	-	-	-

	% Inc.over		14.65	-	-	-
Kh-2021 LSVT	Navsari	9.94	8.58	0.51	1.51	8.88
	Waghai	10.92*	8.87	0.71	2.08	11.91
	Paria	12.12	10.75	0.51	1.51	7.30
	Mean	10.99(3)	9.4 (3)	-	-	-
	% Inc.over		16.91	-	-	-
Kh-2022 LSVT	Navsari	12.17*	10.11	0.71	2.09	10.68
	Waghai	7.80	7.88	0.77	2.27	13.87
	Paria	11.81	10.44	0.51	1.51	7.49
	Mean	10.59 (3)	9.48 (3)	-	-	-
	% Inc.over		11.71	-	-	-
Over all mean (9)		10.02	8.73	-	-	-
Over all % inc. over			14.8	-	-	-
Frequency of top non-significant group			0/9			

*Significantly superior @ 5 % than check

Table 3 presents the ancillary observations of Navsari Pari (NT-1) in comparison with the national check Konkan Haritparni. The results indicated that NT-1 recorded comparatively lower leaf length (27.34 cm) and width (14.42 cm) than the check variety (30.10 cm and 16.54 cm, respectively). However, NT-1 exhibited a substantially higher number of total leaves per plant (34.73) compared to Konkan Haritparni (21.87), indicating better vegetative proliferation. Similarly, fresh weight of leaves with petiole (1532.16 g) and without petiole (645.06 g) per plant were higher in NT-1 than in the check (1365.71 g and 491.41 g, respectively), suggesting greater biomass accumulation. In contrast, single leaf weight without petiole was higher in Konkan Haritparni (22.51 g) than in NT-1 (18.55 g), reflecting comparatively larger individual leaf size in the check variety. Importantly, NT-1 recorded higher corm and cormel yield per plant (1.07 kg) as compared to Konkan Haritparni (0.87 kg), indicating its superior yield potential under the given conditions. Overall, the findings highlight the advantage of NT-1 in terms of leaf production and total biomass, which ultimately contributed to enhanced corm yield.

Table 3: Ancillary observations of the Navsari Pari (NT-1) and national check variety

Sr.No.	Characteristics	Navsari Pari (NT-1)	Konkan Haritparni (NC)
1	Length of leaf (cm)	27.34 (24.80-29.35)	30.10 (27.89-31.42)
2	Width of leaf (cm)	14.42 (11.92-16.57)	16.54 (14.81-19.13)
3	Number of total leaves per plant	34.73 (32.00-38.10)	21.87 (20.44-24.90)
4	Fresh weight of leaf with petiole per plant (g)	1532.16 (1464.43-1572.47)	1365.71 (1258.13-1427.60)
5	Fresh weight of leaf without petiole per plant (g)	645.06 (587.10-702.40)	491.41 (454.80-564.35)
6	Single leaf weight without petiole (g)	18.55 (17.98-19.54)	22.51 (22.18-22.90)
7.	Corm and cormel yield/plant (kg)	1.07 (0.80-1.40)	0.87 (0.44-1.40)

Biochemical Quality

Biochemical evaluation revealed that NT-1 recorded 7.83 % starch, 36.49 % dry matter, 5.46 % protein and 1.60 % fibre content in leaves. Higher dry matter and starch content are desirable traits

which contribute to better cooking quality and energy value of the crop. The calcium oxalate content (0.258 %) was found to be moderate. Calcium oxalate is responsible for acidity in aroid crops; therefore moderate levels improve palatability and consumer acceptance. Similar findings on the relationship between oxalate content and eating quality of tannia leaves have been reported in previous studies.

This variety has erect plant type, soft leaf structure and more number of leaves (34.73) per plant (Table 3). From Fig. 1 and 2, it can be said that it contains high amount of leaves starch (8.15 %), low fibre (1.65 %) and in corm high starch content as well as good cooking quality as compare to check. Similar results were also reported by Agueguia *et al.* (1992), Boakye *et al.* (2017) and Godson *et al.* (2019).

Fig. 1 and 2: Comparative performance of quality parameters between NT- 1 and Konkan Haritparni

Source: Central Instrument Laboratory, Soil Science & Agricultural Chemistry, N.M.C.A., NAU, Navsari

It showed tolerant reaction against Aphid and resistant against corm rot and phytophthora leaf blight (Fig. 3 and Table 4). Similar finding was also noticed by Misra *et al.* (2008) in taro.

Fig. 3: Performance of the Navsari Pari (NT-1) and Konkan Haritparni against Corm Rot Disease and Phytophthora Leaf Blight (%)**Table 4:** Performance of the Navsari Pari (NT-1) and Konkan Haritparni against Aphid index

Insect-pests	Experiment & Year	Location	Aphid index	
			Navsari Pari (NT-1)	Konkan Haritparni (NC)
Aphid	PET, 2019	Navsari	0.57 ± 0.64	0.74 ± 0.79
	SSVT, 2020		0.56 ± 0.69	0.68 ± 0.73
	LSVT, 2021		0.48 ± 0.63	0.73 ± 0.77
	LSVT, 2022		0.58 ± 0.69	0.56 ± 0.60
	SSVT, 2020	Waghai	0.60 ± 0.72	0.72 ± 0.83
	LSVT, 2021		0.59 ± 0.69	0.72 ± 0.72
	LSVT, 2022		0.52 ± 0.67	0.79 ± 0.82
	LSVT, 2021	Paria	0.66 ± 0.76	0.92 ± 0.97
LSVT, 2022	0.77 ± 0.86		0.80 ± 0.88	

*Pest population of aphid was recorded negligible in both the genotype at Navsari, Waghai and Paria centre during the year 2019, 2020, 2021 and 2022.

Molecular Characterization

Molecular analysis using ISSR markers revealed considerable polymorphism among tannia genotypes. Several primers generated clear and reproducible banding patterns useful for genetic differentiation. In NT-1, ISSR primer UBC-810 amplified a unique band at 558 bp which was absent in other accessions, confirming its genetic distinctness. DNA fingerprinting plays an important role in varietal identification, germplasm conservation and protection of plant genetic resources. The presence of unique molecular markers for NT-1 indicates its potential value for breeding programmes and varietal authentication.

DNA fingerprinting profile of tannia varieties was carried out through RAPD marker depicted in Fig. 4. showing the presence of allele 540 bp specific in tannia genotype NT-1, whereas, counter allele is absent in genotype Konkan Haritparni. Therefore, the DNA fingerprinting profile of tannia showing distinctness between Navsari Pari (NT-1) and Konkan Haritparni. ISSR primer UBC 807 generated a prominent bands of 805bp in NT-11 and Navsari Pari, that was absent in Konkan Haritparni. ISSR primer UBC 808 and 809 showed monomorphic bands. ISSR primer UBC 810 generated a prominent bands of 1651bp in NT-11 and Navsari Pari, that was absent in Konkan Haritparni. ISSR primer UBC 811 generated a prominent bands of 1308bp in Navsari Pari and Konkan Haritparni, that was absent in NT-11. Unique band of 300bp was amplified by UBC 811 in Konkan Haritparni, that was absent in NT-11. ISSR primer UBC 812 generated a prominent bands of 1483bp in NT-11 and Navsari Pari, that was absent in Konkan Haritparni as depicted in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4 : RAPD Profiling with OPH 19, L-100bp ladder (1) NT- 1, (2) Konkan Haritparni.

Fig 5: ISSR Profiling of Tannia produced by ISSR primers

Note: L-100bp ladder, 1:NT-11, 2:Navsari Pari, 3:Konkan Haritparni

CONCLUSION

Navsari Pari is a recent variety released and notified in Gujarat State for its leaf purpose. It has recorded high green leaves yield over

national check Konkan Haritparni. It also having medium plant height, soft leaf structure with more numbers of tillers per plant, erect plant type and suitable for intercropping. This

variety was found to have good quality leaves for marketable as well as cooking traits and preferable to consumer test against Konkan Haritparni. In this way, for leaf purpose it is a new variety as compared to others which are generally used for corm purpose in India.

NOTE: (Data availability statement) Data included are referenced in article.

• **Conflict of Interest Statement:** The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Agueguia A., Fatokun C. A., Hahn S. K. 1992. Protein analysis of ten cocoyam, *Xanthosoma sagittifolium* (L.) Schott and *Colocasia esculenta* (L.) Schott genotypes. Root crops for food security in Africa. *Proc. of the 5th Triennial Symp.*, Kampala, Uganda, p. 348.
2. Boakye A. A., Gudjónsdóttir M., Skytte J. L., Chronakis L. S., Wireko-Manu F. D., Oduro I. 2017. Characteristics of *Xanthosoma sagittifolium* roots during cooking, using physiochemical analysis, uniaxial compression, multispectral imaging and low field NMR spectroscopy. *J. Food Sci. and Technol.*, 54 (9): 2670-2683, doi:10.1007/S13197-017-2704-7.
3. Godson Emeka Nwofia, Queen Udodirim Okwu and Emmanuel Ukaobasi Mbah. 2019. Response of Thirteen Tannia Accessions to Variations in Planting Date in the Humid Tropics. *Open Agriculture*, 4: 213–226.
4. Green, B. O. 2003. Taxonomic and nutritional analysis of certain tuber crops in the Niger Delta of Nigeria. *African J. Environ. Studies*, 4: 120-122.
5. Mbouobda, H. D., Boudjeko, T., Djocgoue, P. F., Tsafack, T. J. J., Omokolo, D. N. 2007. Morphological characterization and agronomical evaluation of cocoyam (*Xanthosoma sagittifolium* (L.) Schott) germplasm in Cameroon. *J. Biological Sci.*, 7: 27-33.
6. Misra, R. S., Sharma, K. and Mishra, A. K. 2008. Phytophthora Leaf Blight of Taro (*Colocasia esculenta*) –A Review. *The Asian and Australasian Journal of Plant Science and Biotechnology*, 2 (2): 55-63.
7. Solomon Fantaw, Amsalu Nebiyu and Tewodros Mulualem. 2014. Estimates of genetic components for yield and yield related traits of Tannia (*Xanthosoma sagittifolium* (L.) Schott) genotypes at Jimma, Southwest Ethiopia. *Afr. J. Agric. Res.*, 10 (1): 23-30.
8. Sreena, K. S., Shalini, P. P. and Rajasree, G. 2023. Tuberisation Pattern of Tannia (*Xanthosoma sagittifolium* (L.) Schott) in Response to Crop Management Practices in the South Central Laterites (AEU 9) of Kerala, India. *International Journal of Environment and Climate Change*, 13 (9), 1876–1883. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ijec/2023/v13i92443>.